

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY AND INFORMATION RESOURCES

ANNUAL REPORT 2010–2011

A word cloud centered around the acronym **CLIR**. The words are arranged in a circular pattern around the central text. The colors of the words vary, including shades of green, orange, and yellow. The words include:

- public learning Council
- institutions landscape forward-looking DLF
- practice opportunities knowledge
- virtual Building Resources environment institutional
- types new
- communities cultural
- trust organization teaching
- independent Library
- transform leadership collaboration
- higher transcend
- create organizations
- solutions professional
- forge environments

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THE COUNCIL ON LIBRARY AND INFORMATION RESOURCES (CLIR) grew out of the 1997 merger of the Commission on Preservation and Access (CPA) and the Council on Library Resources (CLR). Over the years, CPA and CLR, in partnership with libraries, archives, and other information providers, had advocated collaborative approaches to preserving the nation's intellectual heritage and strengthening the many components of its information system. CLIR was founded to continue this tradition of support for a national information system and a seamless web of information resources, of which all libraries and archives are a part.

The convening role is central to CLIR's mission. CLIR brings together experts from around the country and around the world and asks them to turn their intelligence to the problems that libraries, archives, and information organizations face as they integrate digital resources and services into their well-established print-based environments.

CLIR urges individuals to look beyond the immediate challenges and imagine the most desirable outcomes for the users of libraries and archives—to be rigorously practical and to dream.

* Term ended November 2010

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ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

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LETTER FROM THE CHAIRMAN

Stephen Nichols
Chairman of the Board

September 2011 marked the 55th birthday of the Council on Library Resources (CLR), CLIR's precursor organization. I recently read a fascinating account of the Council's founding written by former CLIR President Deanna Marcum.¹ Much of her piece focuses on the forces that led to the Council's formation, and in particular, on the ideas of Louis Wright, a former director the Folger Shakespeare Theater and conceptual father of CLR. Wright's incisive observations, recorded in letters and presentations from the 1950s and revealed in the historical account, remain stunningly relevant.

Wright maintained that university libraries were competing with one another and, in the process, were spending large sums of money. He believed that "research libraries faced serious problems that required a new overarching organization built on intellect and conviction, not on pretentious notions about professionalism or representation of the various segments of the population."²

In 1954, Wright secured Ford Foundation funding for a meeting of 50 prominent librarians, administrative officers, and scholars to make "useful plans for solving some of the problems that perplex all libraries that have the complex problems of gathering, preserving, and disseminating research materials."³ The meeting yielded a formidable list of recommendations, all needing time and money to address. Wright then convened a second, smaller meeting to discuss creating an independent agency to tackle the problems directly. He proposed the idea to Ford, and in May 1956 the foundation announced its intent to award funds to establish the Council on Library Resources the following year.

The themes articulated by Wright continue to motivate CLIR's efforts, as Chuck Henry illustrates in his message from the president. Now, as then, CLIR's work at the nexus of libraries, scholarship, and technology

¹ Deanna B. Marcum. Reclaiming the Research Library: The Founding of the Council on Library Resources. Presentation at the Library History Seminar, Tuscaloosa, Alabama, March 31, 1995. Available at www.clir.org/about/CLRhistoryDM95.pdf.

² *Ibid*, p. 2

³ Typescript of Wright's introductory remarks at the Folger Library, January 15, 1955, as quoted in Marcum 1995.

acknowledges that solving “problems that perplex all libraries” requires working across disciplines, institutions, professions, and geographic boundaries.

CLIR’s work would not be possible without the support of its sponsoring institutions and funding agencies. On behalf of the Board, I want to thank the foundations, government agencies, and sponsors that have placed their confidence in CLIR and have supported us so generously.

Stephen Nichols

November 2011

MESSAGE FROM THE PRESIDENT

Charles Henry
President

CLIBIR aspires to transform the information landscape to support the advancement of knowledge.

This, the new vision statement for CLIR, builds upon the traditional strengths of the Council but describes an organization more integral to the changes now taking place in higher education and more involved in managing them. The vision statement is a result of a two-day retreat, held in the spring of 2011, during which the CLIR Board of Directors met with the CLIR staff to refresh the organization's vision and mission statements, and to identify our most salient values as we move forward. Those goals were achieved. The new mission statement is similarly invigorated:

CLIR is an independent, nonprofit organization that forges strategies to enhance research, teaching, and learning environments in collaboration with libraries, cultural institutions, and communities of higher learning.

The values that the Board and staff defined are pivotal to CLIR's ongoing and new programs and projects:

CLIR promotes forward-looking collaborative solutions that transcend disciplinary, institutional, professional, and geographic boundaries in support of the public good. In pursuing its mission, CLIR is committed to building trust, retaining independence, fostering collaboration, cultivating effective leadership, and capitalizing on strategic opportunities.

Intimations of this deeper involvement with the various constituencies of higher education can be gleaned from my President's Letter in the 2010 Annual Report. At the time, I stated that CLIR would seek partners to develop methods, guidelines, and recommendations that will help academic leaders instantiate sustainable communities of practice to produce a new, more rational system of higher education, including a robust digital environment designed for teaching and research. I noted that this work might involve the creation of new types of communities—virtual organizations that transcend geographic and institutional boundaries and that share technical and social elements.

A year ago, one of the new opportunities that held promise for helping achieve these goals was the reintegration of the Digital Library Federation (DLF) as a program within CLIR. By reuniting with CLIR, DLF brought to the Council a network of technical expertise and an extraordinary pool of

talent that could focus on the complex infrastructure needs of higher education. During the past year, this is precisely what we have accomplished.

Two examples are indicative. This year, The Andrew W. Mellon Foundation awarded CLIR a grant to build a prototype for the Digital Public Library of America (DPLA). As described in its prospectus, the DPLA aspires to “make the cultural and scientific heritage of humanity available, free of charge, to all. By adhering to the fundamental principle of free and universal access to knowledge, it will promote education in the broadest sense of the term.” CLIR, through DLF, is currently constructing a functional prototype for this project, building on research from the Digital Collections and Content/Opening History project funded by Institute of Museum and Library Services. Also this year, the Alfred P. Sloan Foundation awarded CLIR a grant to research curricula used to prepare students interested in data curation, and to investigate current practices at active data-curation centers and programs. We expect that this research will become foundational for subsequent grants that support the training of a new cadre of data-curation professionals.

CLIR’s cooperative agreement with the National Endowment for the Humanities to conduct a rigorous analysis of the endowment’s Digging into Data program is also thematically and tactically linked to facets of the DPLA and, because of the dependency of this research on very large-scale datasets, pertains to the data-curation work we are undertaking.

CLIR continues to align its past research—in this case, recommendations in *The Idea of Order* for rethinking research libraries, and in *Working Together or Apart* for examining what is needed to support computationally intensive research in the humanities—with practical applications in service to libraries, information technology organizations, and scholars in higher education.

This is an exciting nexus of research and practice, complementing our flourishing programs that include Hidden Collections, original source dissertation fellowships, the Zipf Fellowship, the Frye Leadership Institute, leadership for members of the Council of Independent Colleges, and our postdoctoral program. It is an agenda that CLIR, as a trusted, neutral organization, is uniquely positioned to execute, consonant with our mission and values, and thoughtfully articulate of our vision.

Charles Henry
November 2011

THE PROGRAMS

July 1, 2010–June 30, 2011

CYBERINFRASTRUCTURE

Objective: Define the base technologies of computation and communication, the software programs, and the data curation and preservation programs that are national in scale and needed to manage very large-scale multimedia data sets, especially pertaining to the digital record of our cultural heritage.

Digital Library Federation Program

The Digital Library Federation (DLF), which merged with CLIR in July 2009, focuses on the technological aspects of developing, sustaining, and aggregating digital resources; promoting standards, protocols, and best practices; and supporting digital architectures that are open source, extensible, and interoperable. The DLF has been integral to CLIR's work on recent grants for research and training to support a new data curation profession, research on linked data, and efforts to develop a prototype for the Digital Public Library of America.

The DLF Forum continues to serve as an important venue for better understanding the elements and complexity of digital library evolution and for exchange and collaboration on practical work. The 2010 Fall Forum was held November 1–3 in Palo Alto, California.

In March 2011, a website for the DLF community was established at www.diglib.org.

Study and Workshop on Linked Data

In March 2011, The Andrew W. Mellon Foundation awarded grants to CLIR and to Stanford University to commission a survey and conduct a workshop, respectively, on linked data. The aims of the survey and workshop were to better understand the current landscape for linked data work and to develop specifications, requirements, and a basic technical design for a multinational, multi-institutional prototype demonstrating the viability and efficacy of a linked data environment for improving discovery and navigation.

The survey, which was commissioned as background for the workshop, reviews and analyzes existing projects and programs that use semantic web, linked data, and Resource Description Framework (RDF) Triples Technologies—elements critical to a linked data environment that will enable improved discovery and navigation across multiple information genres and formats.

The workshop was held June 27–July 1, 2011, at Stanford University. Discussion focused on outlining a national agenda for developing linked data environments, reducing redundancy of effort, and creating a more sophisticated context in which practitioners and planners can develop future projects.

The survey and a report from the workshop are available at <http://www.clir.org/pubs/abstract/pub152abst.html>.

Building Data Curation Skills

In April 2011, the Alfred P. Sloan Foundation awarded CLIR funds for research on how to build capacity for data curation in varying disciplines. Most graduate programs in the sciences, social sciences, and humanities are not designed to cultivate the data management skills of their students, or even to help them understand why such skills are important to their fields of study. Nonetheless, in every discipline, at least some professionals must master the complex demands related to the creation, access, reuse, and preservation of digital research data that have traditionally been the purview of the library and information technology professions and of schools of library, information, and computer science.

The data curation project consists of three interrelated activities that will be completed by summer 2013. The first activity is an environmental scan of professional development needs and of education and training opportunities for digital curation in the academy. The second is an anthropological study of five sites where digital curation activities are under way. The third is a report that analyzes the results of the two research efforts and includes a proposal, informed by the findings, for amending the curriculum for CLIR's Postdoctoral Fellowship in Academic Libraries program.

ARL/DLF E-Science Institute

In early 2011, CLIR's DLF Program joined with the Association for Research Libraries (ARL) to create the ARL/DLF E-Science Institute, which launched July 1, 2011. The institute seeks to give participants a basis for developing a sound strategic approach to exploring and supporting e-science within their organizations. It comprises a set of designed learning experiences that take small teams of individuals through a process that strengthens their e-science support role. Specific member institutions of ARL and CLIR/DLF are funding design of the institute's training program.

Assessment of Digging into Data Challenge

In January 2010, CLIR entered a cooperative agreement with the National Endowment for the Humanities (NEH) Office of Digital Humanities to provide a strategic assessment of the Digging into Data (DID) Challenge, a grant competition that had been jointly sponsored by NEH, the U.K.'s Joint Information Systems Committee (JISC), the U.S. National Science Foundation, and Canada's Social Sciences and Humanities Research Council. The goals of the DID Challenge are to encourage international, multidisciplinary collaborations that explore the application of computational techniques to large corpora and to begin to understand the kinds of research that are possible when advanced search algorithms are applied to these corpora. The program's sponsors announced the first eight awards in December 2009. Encouraged by the success of the inaugural challenge, the cooperating agencies have joined with four additional sponsors to fund a second cycle for the program. The next grant recipients will be announced in December 2011.

The CLIR–NEH cooperative assessment will address how well the DID Challenge met its objectives and identify the next steps agencies and researchers might take to best support continued development in this area. In early 2011, CLIR staff visited all eight project teams funded in the program's first cycle. In June 2011, the teams delivered public reports on their findings in Washington, DC, and eight expert respondents delivered assessments of these reports. CLIR held focus group meetings with project principal investigators and expert respondents before and after this meeting.

In autumn 2011 and spring 2012, CLIR will issue two final reports. The first report will discuss implications of the findings for the future of computationally intensive scholarship in the humanities, and for the roles of academic institutions and public and private funding agencies in fostering this research. The second will be a technical summary that addresses the administrative history of the program and gives an account of the study methodology, summary of findings, next steps, and recommendations.

Infrastructure for Humanities Scholarship

CLIR continued its work with Tufts University on a process to identify what is needed to advance an infrastructure to support humanities scholarship, with a particular focus on the classics. In October 2010, CLIR hosted a meeting of classics scholars to discuss a literature review of digital projects in the classics and to outline goals and objectives for a strategic plan that describes the technical requirements for a classics infrastructure.

The literature review, written by Alison Babeu of Tufts University's Perseus Project, was circulated broadly for comment. A final version,

issued in August 2011, is available at <http://www.clir.org/pubs/abstract/pub150abst.html>. Work on the strategic plan continues under the leadership of Gregory Crane, editor-in-chief of the Perseus Digital Library, Tufts University. A final version of the plan is anticipated in early 2012.

NEW MODELS

Objective: Extrapolate from an array of CLIR's findings and other related research how academic organizations, institutions, behaviors, and culture may evolve.

DPLA Prototype

The Digital Public Library of America (DPLA) is envisioned as a large-scale digital library that will “make the cultural and scientific heritage of humanity available, free of charge, to all.” Planning for the DPLA began late in 2010. The Berkman Center for Internet & Society at Harvard University serves as the secretariat. The DPLA is currently organized by six workstreams that are defined and coordinated through a steering committee. The workstreams include audience and participation; financial/business models; governance; legal issues; technical aspects; and content and scope. In May 2011, the steering committee announced a “Beta Sprint” to solicit models, prototypes, tools, and interfaces that demonstrate how the DPLA might index and provide access to a wide range of broadly distributed content.

The DLF Program and the Center for Informatics Research in Science and Scholarship (CIRSS) at the Graduate School of Library and Information Science at the University of Illinois submitted a prototype to the Beta Sprint, which was among those chosen for presentation at the October 2011 DPLA Plenary Meeting. The DLF/CIRSS project prototype leverages the Institute of Museum and Library Services’ Digital Collections and Content (IMLS DCC) resource and DLF Aquifer content as a core collection for the DPLA. The IMLS DCC, launched in 2003, is an aggregation of digital collections from libraries, museums, and archives, supported by IMLS and developed through a collaboration between CIRSS and the University of Illinois Library.

As part of the project to develop the prototype, CLIR commissioned a comparative report that reviews the research on and practical efforts to aggregate large-scale collections. The report, to be published in late 2011 or early 2012, will shed light on how and why large-scale aggregation projects succeed or fail. The report will also identify potential content providers for the DPLA and will estimate the time, effort, and other costs required to ingest these resources into the resulting prototype.

THE NEXT SCHOLAR

Objective: Explore and assess new methodologies, emerging fields of inquiry, intellectual strategies involving data gathering and collaboration, and modes of communication, including sharing of research data and publishing models, that are likely to define the next generation of scholars.

Postdoctoral Fellowship in Academic Libraries Program

CLIR Postdoctoral Library Fellows work on projects that forge, renovate, and strengthen connections between academic library collections and their users. The program offers scholars who have recently earned their Ph.D.s a chance to work in academic libraries on projects related to their disciplines that benefit both the scholar and the library. The fellows have the opportunity to develop research models, collaborate with information specialists, and explore new career opportunities. Participating libraries benefit from the expertise of accomplished scholars who can invigorate approaches to collection use and teaching, contribute field-specific knowledge, and provide insight into the future of scholarship.

2010–2011 Postdoctoral Fellows in Academic Libraries

<i>New Fellows</i>	<i>Host Institution</i>
Andrew Asher	Bucknell University
Tamar Boyadjian	University of California, Los Angeles
Brian Croxall	Emory University
John Maclachlan	McMaster University
Julia Osman	Arizona State Library, Archives and Public Records
Yi Shen	Johns Hopkins University
Mike Snowdon	McMaster University
<i>Continuing Fellows</i>	<i>Host Institution</i>
Anne Bruder	Bryn Mawr College
Daniel Chamberlain	Occidental College
Timothy F. Jackson	University of Nebraska-Lincoln
Lori Jahnke	The College of Physicians of Philadelphia
Noah Shenker	McMaster University

Cataloging Hidden Special Collections and Archives: Building a New Research Environment

CLIR's Cataloging Hidden Special Collections and Archives Program supports cataloging projects that expose unknown or underutilized cultural materials to communities of scholars, students, and other users who need them for their work. The program, which is funded by The Andrew W. Mellon Foundation, completed its third review cycle in 2010. The review panel selected 17 projects to receive a total of \$4 million in awards.

Since the program's inception, 47 projects, representing a wide range of institutions from across the United States, have been funded. The projects have already made impressively large volumes of cultural materials in diverse formats accessible to scholars.

Work continues on a multiyear study to describe successful strategies for engaging users with collections. The study, titled "Observations on Scholarly Engagement with Hidden Special Collections and Archives," is being undertaken by a team of former participants in CLIR's Postdoctoral Fellowship in Academic Libraries Program. A second interim report on the study, submitted to CLIR in June 2011, is available on the Hidden Collections program website (<http://www.clir.org/hiddencollections/engagement/SEdocuments.html>).

In the coming year, the study team will focus on three subject areas that are well represented among funded projects: civil rights, natural history, and literature. Rather than reporting their findings to CLIR, the team

2010 Cataloging Hidden Special Collections and Archives Awards

<p>American Museum of Natural History Library: For the People, for Education, for Science: Web Access to the American Museum of Natural History Archives, \$117,600</p>	<p>University of California, Berkeley, University of California Museum of Paleontology: Cataloging Hidden Archives of the University of California Museum of Paleontology, \$236,200</p>
<p>Arizona State University Libraries: Labor Rights Are Civil Rights/Los Derechos de Trabajo Son Derechos Civiles, \$155,600</p>	<p>University of Chicago, on behalf of the Black Metropolis Research Consortium: The “Color Curtain” Processing Project: Unveiling the Archives of Chicago’s Black Metropolis, \$499,500</p>
<p>Eleutherian Mill-Hagley Foundation, Inc., on behalf of the Hagley Museum and Library: Z. Taylor Vinson Transportation Collection Processing Project, \$246,100</p>	<p>University of Nebraska-Lincoln: Major Railroad Archival Collections, \$208,500</p>
<p>J. Paul Getty Trust on behalf of the Getty Research Institute: Open Plan, Open Access: Increasing Researcher Access to Modern Architectural Records, \$154,600</p>	<p>University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill: The Pruitt and Shanks Photographic Collection: The Life of a Southern Region in 140,000 Images, \$78,400</p>
<p>Northeast Historic Film: Moving Images 1938–1940: Amateur Filmmakers Record the New York World’s Fair and its Period, \$186,900</p>	<p>University of Pennsylvania: Promoting Research through Rare Book Cataloging Partnerships, \$490,700</p>
<p>San Diego Historical Society: Enhancing Access to the History of San Diego and the Border Region, \$162,100</p>	<p>The University of Texas at Austin, Harry Ransom Center: Revealing Texas Collections of Comedias Seltas, \$137,100</p>
<p>Smithsonian Institution, on behalf of the Freer Gallery of Art and Arthur M. Sackler Gallery: Islamic Arts of the Book at the Smithsonian: Providing for Research across Disciplines, \$82,500</p>	<p>WGBH Educational Foundation: Exposing Unknown Boston Local TV News Collections, \$311,000</p>
<p>Stanford University: Documenting Mexican American & Latino Civil Rights: Records of the Mexican American Legal Defense and Educational Fund & California Rural Legal Assistance, \$349,300</p>	<p>Yale University, Yale Peabody Museum of Natural History: DNA to Dinosaurs: The Globalization of Science in America and the Development of a University Natural History Museum, \$409,300</p>
<p>Syracuse University: Grove Press and a New American Morality, \$143,100</p>	<hr/> <p>More detail on this year’s funded projects can be found at http://www.clir.org/hiddencollections/awards/index2010.html.</p>

will focus on describing the impact of hidden collections cataloging and related programming for the communities of scholars and students who work with these collections. The teams plan to host a webinar, curate an online exhibit, and submit articles for publication in relevant scholarly and professional journals.

Mellon Dissertation Fellowships

The Mellon Dissertation Fellowship program helps junior scholars in the humanities and related social science fields gain skill and creativity in developing knowledge from original sources; enables dissertation writers to do research wherever relevant sources may be, rather than just where

2010–2011 Mellon Dissertation Fellows

Matthew Amato, University of Southern California
Amy Brady, University of Massachusetts Amherst
Nora Barakat, University of California, Berkeley
Meaghan Brown, Florida State University
Rowan Dorin, Harvard University
Alice Goff, University of California, Berkeley
M. Scott Heerman, University of Maryland,
College Park
Philippa Hetherington, Harvard University
Philip Johnston, Harvard University
Eugenia Kisin, New York University
Konstanze Kunst, University of Pennsylvania
Melissa Lo, Harvard University
Anne Phillips, Duke University
Naomi Pitamber, University of California,
Los Angeles
Lena Suk, Emory University
Gene Tempest, Yale University

financial support is available; encourages more extensive and innovative uses of original sources in libraries, archives, museums, historical societies, and related repositories in the United States and abroad; and provides insight from the viewpoint of doctoral candidates into how scholarly resources can be developed for access most effectively in the future. The fellowship program, now in its eleventh year, has supported 127 graduate students as they carried out their dissertation research in a variety of public and private libraries and archives.

A research study is under way on the Mellon Fellowship Program's first 10 years. Surveys and interviews are being conducted to better understand the fellows' experiences in the program; their introduction to and integration into teaching and research following the fellowship; and methodologies in their field—what has changed, and what has remained constant.

PRESERVATION

Objective: Examine sustainable strategies for preserving all media, analog and traditional, and heightening public awareness of the risks of failing to plan for preservation.

Preserving Recorded Sound Heritage

Since 2004, CLIR has conducted work under contract with the Library of Congress (LC) and the National Recording Preservation Board in support of an ongoing study of the state of recorded sound preservation and restoration. In 2010, CLIR collaborated with LC on the editing and production of *The State of Recorded Sound Preservation in the United States: A National Legacy at Risk in the Digital Age*, the first comprehensive, national-level study of the state of sound recording preservation ever conducted in the United States.

Preservation Symposia

In 2010–2011, CLIR partnered with the Library of Congress in presenting three of its Future Directions Symposia. The first symposium, "Understanding the Physical Environment," in fall 2010, reviewed 25 years of research by the Image Permanence Institute that have produced resources and recommendations now widely used to preserve a broad range of media.

The second conference, "Assessing Options for Large Collections," was held in March 2011. Senior preservation administrators, scientists, digital collection experts, and conservators described options for managing large collections in the context of environmentally controlled remote storage, mass-deacidification treatments, and digitization.

CLIR Chief Information Officers Group Members (as of 6/30/11)

Christopher Barth, Luther College
 Param Bedi, Bucknell University
 Frank Cervone, Perdue University Calumet
 Jim Cubit, Lake Forest College
 Jose Dieudonne, Arcadia University
 Greg Diment, Kalamazoo College
 Charling Chang Fagan, Sarah Lawrence College
 Chris Ferguson, Pacific Lutheran University
 Megan Fitch, Beloit College
 Chip German, Millersville College
 Ronald Griggs, Kenyon College
 Perry Hanson, Brandeis University
 Lee Hisle, Connecticut College
 Rick Holmgren, Allegheny College
 Robert Johnson, Rhodes College
 Kenneth Kochien, Colby-Sawyer College
 Neil McElroy, Lafayette College
 Pam McQuesten, Occidental College
 Kathy Monday, University of Richmond
 Pattie Orr, Baylor University
 Charlotte Slocum Patriquin, Mount Holyoke College
 Rick Provine, DePauw University
 Ravi Ravishanker, Wellesley College
 Robert Renaud, Dickinson College
 Suzanne Rislely, Mitchell College
 Mike Roy, Middlebury College
 Vicki Sells, Sewanee: The University of the South
 Elliott Shore, Bryn Mawr College
 Scott Silverman, Earlham College
 Carol Smith, DePauw University
 Bruce Taggart, Lehigh University
 Gene Wiemers, Bates College
 Frank Wojcik, The College at Brockport, State
 University of New York

The third conference, held in October 2011, focused on the road ahead, as cultural agencies work together to devise strategies for providing broad and long-term access to the mixed collection formats of the 21st century.

CLIR/Library of Congress Fellowship

In spring 2011, CLIR established the CLIR/Library of Congress Fellowship, which supports original-source dissertation research in the humanities or related social sciences in the Preservation Research and Testing Division of the Preservation Directorate at the Library. The fellowship is offered as part of the Mellon Fellowships for Dissertation Research in Original Sources. Amy Brady, of the University of Massachusetts Amherst, was awarded the fellowship for 2011 for research on America's Federal Theatre and the Proletarian Avant-Garde.

THE EMERGING LIBRARY

Objective: Explore the increasingly swift evolution of the concept of the library with particular focus on its core functions and the possible consequences for staffing, research and teaching, and economic modeling.

Workshops on Participatory Design in Academic Libraries

CLIR has launched a new workshop series, based on its successful workshops on faculty research behavior and undergraduate research practices begun in 2007. Led by Nancy Fried Foster, director of anthropological research at the University of Rochester's River Campus Libraries, the new workshops provide attendees with an overview of the participatory design process and strategies for including faculty members, graduate students, undergraduates, and library staff in the design process. The workshops feature extensive interaction among participants and between participants and research subjects. The first workshop, held in April 2011, was well received. Since 2007, 207 people have participated in the workshop series.

CLIR Chief Information Officers Group

CLIR's Chief Information Officers Group is composed of 33 directors of organizations that have merged their library and technology units on liberal arts college campuses. The group met in October 2010 and April 2011 to discuss common concerns and to exchange ideas about possible solutions for organizational and policy problems unique to their campus environments. They explored such topics as open access; how the recession has affected organizational structure, technology, business strategies, and attitudes; cloud computing; portals versus Web 2.0; strategies for measuring the use and effectiveness of services; and ideas for prioritizing services. Throughout the year members exchange ideas and solutions through a listserv.

LEADERSHIP

Objective: Investigate and seek to define the skills and expertise needed to best administer, inspire, and inform the next generation.

Leadership through New Communities of Knowledge

Launched in July 2009 as a partnership between CLIR and the Council of Independent Colleges (CIC), this program offers professional development opportunities for library staff at small-to-midsize private colleges and universities. Since the program's inception, CLIR has sent participants from CIC schools to numerous workshops on data curation, work restructuring, archival practice, undergraduate research behavior, and information fluency.

Several workshops were offered from July 1, 2010–June 30, 2011: Work Restructuring in the Library Workshop (July 7–8, 2010, and May 23–25, 2011); Archives for Non-Archivists Workshop (October 28–29, 2010, and June 14–15, 2011); and Undergraduate Research Behavior Workshop (November 8–9, 2010). CLIR cosponsored with CIC the Information Fluency in the Disciplines Workshop in Literature (February 10–12, 2011) and Information Fluency in the Disciplines Workshop in History (March 3–5, 2011). Scholarships were offered to the University of North Carolina's Digital Curation Institute (January 5–6, 2011).

Project staff also began planning for a symposium on the future of the liberal arts college library, held October 10–11, 2011, in Milwaukee, Wisconsin.

The project is supported with funds from the Institute of Museum and Library Services.

Frye Leadership Institute

The Frye Leadership Institute, created to prepare and develop the next generation of leaders in libraries, information services, and higher education, welcomed its first class of students in 1999. Institutes were held annually thereafter until 2009.

In 2010, the Frye Institute took a one-year hiatus to develop and articulate a new program that addresses higher education's leadership needs in an era of unprecedented change. The institute resumed with a new curriculum June 5–10, 2011, in Atlanta, Georgia. The new program engages individuals who are already leaders in their profession and seeks to further develop their skills, particularly in the area of advocacy. The institute addresses challenges in higher education through a variety of topics, empowering librarians and information technologists to start conversations

Frye Leadership Institute Participants 2011

Amy Badertscher, Kenyon College
 John Barden, University of Rochester
 Fred Brittain, University of Maine at Farmington
 George Claffey, Charter Oak State College / CT
 Distance Learning Consortium
 David Consiglio, Bryn Mawr College
 Diane Duesterhoeft, St. Mary's University
 Katherine Furlong, Lafayette College
 Diane Gal, State University of New York, Empire
 State College
 Anna Getselman, Emory University
 Andrew Goodenow, University of Missouri-
 Kansas City
 Emily Gore, Clemson University
 Gentry Holbert, Spring Hill College
 Stephen Houser, University of Southern Maine
 Julie Kane, Sweet Briar College
 Rebecca Kennison, Columbia University
 Melissa Levine, University of Michigan Library,
 MPublishing
 Veronica Longenecker, Millersville University
 Michael Notarius, State University of New York,
 Information Technology Exchange Center
 Carla Rathbone, Clemson University
 Rosemary Rocchio, University of California,
 Los Angeles
 Judith Thomas, University of Virginia
 Joe Williams, University of North Carolina at
 Greensboro

and take action on issues that are important not only to their own institutions but also to the entire higher education community.

The Frye Leadership Institute is cosponsored by CLIR, EDUCAUSE, and Emory University.

Rick Peterson Fellowship

In 2011 CLIR, in partnership with the National Institute for Technology in Liberal Education (NITLE), established a fellowship in honor of Richard (Rick) Allen Peterson. The fellowship will be awarded annually to an early-career information technology (IT) professional or librarian who has reached beyond traditional boundaries to resolve a significant challenge facing digital libraries. The fellowship supports participation in the annual NITLE Symposium and in CLIR's DLF Forum.

The 2011 fellowship was granted to Meghan Frazer, digital resource librarian at Kenyon College. Peterson, who died in early 2011, was an active promoter of collaboration in the area of IT services and digital libraries. He last served as chief technology officer at Washington and Lee University.

Zipf Fellowship

Kathleen Fear, a Ph.D. candidate in the School of Information at the University of Michigan, was selected to receive the A. R. Zipf Fellowship in Information Management for 2011. Her research focuses on how scientific data can best be preserved, managed, and accessed.

The Zipf Fellowship is awarded annually to a graduate student in a field of information management or systems who best exemplifies the ideals of Al Zipf, the information science pioneer for whom the award is named.

Rovelstad Scholarship in International Librarianship

Timothy Thompson, a dual-degree master's student in library science and Latin American and Caribbean studies at Indiana University, was awarded the 2011 Rovelstad Scholarship in International Librarianship. Thompson is studying advanced Portuguese at the University of Brasilia and undertaking fieldwork for his master's thesis. He is conducting a survey and meta-analysis of major digital library projects being developed in Brazil and their social impact on community development.

Instituted in 2002, the Rovelstad Scholarship encourages library students who have an interest in international library work by enabling them to attend the World Library and Information Congress, the annual meeting of the International Federation of Library Associations and Institutions.

2011 Sponsors' Symposium: Collaborative Opportunities amidst Economic Pressures

The 2011 Sponsors' Symposium, held April 6 in Arlington, Virginia, examined how institutions are engaging in deep collaboration to share resources and expertise with the goal of improving services and realizing benefits that extend beyond the individual organization. Speakers included Martha Sites, from the University of Virginia; Lori Jahnke, from the College of Physicians of Philadelphia; and Heike Neuroth, from the University Library of Göttingen, Germany.

PARTNERSHIPS

Open Academic Publishing in the European Network

CLIR is represented on the EU Scientific Board overseeing the reconceptualization of major academic presses in the European Union and United Kingdom.

Scholarly Communication Institute

CLIR President Chuck Henry served on the planning committee for the Scholarly Communication Institute (SCI), which in 2011 was titled "New Model Scholarly Communication: Road Map for Change." The SCI began in 2003 with the goal of providing an opportunity for scholars and leaders in scholarly disciplines and societies, academic libraries, information technology, and higher education administration to design, test, and implement strategies that advance the humanities through the use of innovative technologies. Since 2006, the University of Virginia has hosted SCI, which is under the direction of Abby Smith-Rumsey. Information about the SCI is available at <http://www.uvasci.org/>.

Medical Heritage Digital Collaborative (NEH)

The Medical Heritage Digital Collaborative (MHDC) is a partnership of nine institutions striving to connect history of medicine collections in an open-access digital environment. The partnering institutions possess a wealth of physicians' papers, correspondence, institutional records, books, and images integral to understanding the history and social context of western medicine. The collections have been geographically and technologically isolated from one another, which has presented significant obstacles for researchers in the study of the medical humanities. Digitally linking collections across institutions will increase efficiency in discovery and expand access to underused materials, creating a partnership model for engaging scholars in a multi-institutional collaboration.

The MHDC will bridge institutional and professional boundaries to support changing scholarly needs in response to emerging technologies. This innovative collaboration will make it possible to engage scholars in platform design and selection of content, to rationalize and manage collections

across institutions, and to provide the support necessary to engage smaller organizations and specialized collections.

In April 2011, the Medical Heritage Library (MHL), a project of the MHDC, received a Digital Humanities Start-up Grant from the National Endowment for the Humanities. The grant will support planning activities among the nine MHDC institutions, CLIR, and a scholarly advisory committee to continue developing the MHL.

Federated Research and Educational Depository System

The Federated Research and Educational Depository System (FREDS) is a national effort of research universities, corporations, and open source organizations that aims to construct a federation of archives devoted to the preservation of the digital scholarly record in higher education.

The archives will be distinct: each will run on a unique platform for an overall fail safe operation, but all will be aligned and available to take on the data of another in case of a catastrophic event: an amalgam of independence and virtual aggregation. Annual audits and other mechanisms will assure clients of the trustworthiness of the data, to an extent where the digital objects so archived can adequately replace their analog versions, for a tremendous cost saving to higher education.

CLIR took part in planning meetings for FREDS in November 2010 and February 2011. DuraSpace, Emory University, Indiana University, Stanford University, the University of Michigan, and University of Virginia are among the other institutions collaborating in the effort.

ADVISORY GROUPS

AS OF JUNE 30, 2011

Academic Librarians Advisory Committee

Tyrone Cannon
University of San Francisco

Charles Henry
CLIR

Robert Renaud
Dickinson College

Connie Vinita Dowell
San Diego State University

Michael D. Miller
California Polytechnic University

Joanne Schneider
Colgate University

A. R. Zipf Fellowship Selection Committee

Christine Borgman
University of California, Los Angeles

Deanna B. Marcum
Library of Congress

Rena Zipf

Digital Library Federation Program Advisory Committee

Eric Celeste
Minneapolis, MN

Katherine Kott
Stanford University

Diana Oblinger
EDUCAUSE

Sayed Choudhury
Johns Hopkins University

Clifford Lynch
Coalition for Networked Information

Elliott Shore
Bryn Mawr College

Geneva Henry
Rice University

James Neal
Columbia University

John Wilkin
HathiTrust

Joseph King
National Institute for Technology in Liberal
Education

Hidden Collections Review Panel

Rachel Frick
Council on Library and Information
Resources

Geneva Henry
Rice University

Jerome McGann
University of Virginia

Joan Giesecke
University of Nebraska at Lincoln

Michael Keller*
Stanford University

Stephen G. Nichols
Johns Hopkins University

Jacqueline Goldsby
University of Chicago

Mary Kelley
University of Michigan

Elliott Shore
Bryn Mawr College

Charles Henry
Council on Library and Information
Resources

Ronald L. Larsen
University of Pittsburgh

Richard V. Szary
University of North Carolina at
Chapel Hill

**Panelist during preproposal round only*

Mellon Fellowships Selection Committee 2011

Rebecca L. Davis
University of Delaware

June Teufel Dreyer
University of Miami

Charles Henry
Council on Library and Information
Resources

Mark Dimunation
Library of Congress

Nancy Fried Foster
University of Rochester

Stephen G. Nichols
Johns Hopkins University

Roy Domenico
The University of Scranton

Richard Freedman
Haverford College

GRANTS AND CONTRACTS

ACTIVE IN THE PERIOD JULY 1, 2010 TO JUNE 30, 2011

Recipient	Purpose	Authorized	Amount
Amelia Acker Los Angeles, CA	To conduct a literature review on declassified computational tools of possible use to humanists	7/13/2009	\$5,000
American Museum of Natural History New York, NY	2010 Hidden Collections grant to support the project, "For the People, for Education, for Science: Web Access to the American Museum of Natural History Archives"	12/16/2010	\$117,600
Amistad Research Center New Orleans, LA	2008 Hidden Collections grant to support the project, "Working for Freedom: Documenting Civil Rights Organization"	1/23/2009	\$250,000
Arizona State University Libraries Phoenix, AZ	2010 Hidden Collections grant to support the project, "Labor Rights are Civil Rights"	12/16/2010	\$155,600
Avery Research Center for African American History Charleston, SC	2008 Hidden Collections grant to support the project, "Providing Access to African American Collections at the Avery Research Center"	12/1/2008	\$236,920
Brooklyn Historical Society Brooklyn, NY	2009 Hidden Collections grant to support the project, "Uncovering the Secrets of Brooklyn's 19th Century Past: Creation to Consolidation"	11/13/2009	\$440,491
Marta Brunner Los Angeles, CA	To serve as coordinator of CLIR's monthly Postdoctoral Fellows Synchronous Sessions	10/7/2009	\$2,400
California Digital Library Oakland, CA	2009 Hidden Collections grant to support the project, "Uncovering California's Environmental Collections: A Collaborative Approach"	11/13/2009	\$446,817
California Historical Society San Francisco, CA	2008 Hidden Collections grant to support the project, "California Ephemera Project"	12/1/2008	\$247,738
Eric Celeste St. Paul, MN	To provide technical assistance with DLF website	12/03/2010	\$9,200
Center for the History of Medicine Boston, MA	2008 Hidden Collections grant to support the project, "Foundations of Public Health Policy"	12/1/2008	\$217,933
Lauren Coats Memphis, TN	To coordinate CLIR's monthly Postdoctoral Synchronous Sessions	10/25/2010	\$2,600
College of Charleston Charleston, SC	2009 Hidden Collections grant to support the cataloging of the library's Jewish Heritage Collection	11/13/2009	\$184,000
David Consiglio Bryn Mawr, PA	To develop and administer two surveys in support of "New Communities of Knowledge" grant	11/17/2010	\$5,000
Cornell University Ithaca, NY	To conduct a joint user needs study of graduate students in the humanities at Cornell and Columbia Universities	1/18/2010	\$15,000

Recipient	Purpose	Authorized	Amount
Emory University Atlanta, GA	2008 Hidden Collections grant to support the project, "Archives from Atlanta, Cradle of the Civil Rights Movement: the papers of Andrew Young, SCLC, and NAACP-Atlanta, GA"	1/23/2009	\$399,172
Nancy Foster Rochester, NY	To conduct one Undergraduate Research Behavior Workshop at Rollins College	7/22/2010	\$3,000
Free Library of Philadelphia Philadelphia, PA	2009 Hidden Collections grant to support the project, "Milestones in 20th Century American Children's Literature at the Free Library of Philadelphia"	11/13/2009	\$264,945
Mike Furlough University Park, PA	To research business planning methods and academic library services that support campus-based publishing and research data management	2/17/2011	\$50,000
George Mason University Fairfax, VA	2009 Hidden Collections grant to support the project, "Uncovering a Forbidden World: Providing Access to East German Art, Culture, and Politics"	11/13/2009	\$76,800
George Mason University Fairfax, VA	To support librarian participation in THATCamp 2010-2011 unconferences	6/11/2010	\$5,000
Getty Research Institute Los Angeles, CA	2008 Hidden Collections grant to support the project, "Uncovering Archives and Rare Photographs: Two Models for Creating Accession-level Finding Aids Using Archivists' Toolkit"	12/1/2008	\$274,889
Getty Research Institute Los Angeles, CA	2010 Hidden Collections grant to support the project, "Open Plan, Open Access: Increasing Researcher Access to Modern Architectural Records"	12/16/2010	\$154,579
Hagley Museum and Library Wilmington, DE	2010 Hidden Collections grant to support the project, "Z. Taylor Vinson Transportation Collection Processing Project"	12/16/2010	\$246,100
Geneva Henry Houston, TX	To conduct research and write a report leading to a prototype proposal for the DPLA Beta Sprint Challenge	6/30/2011	\$7,500
Intelligent Television New York, NY	To organize panels of professionals from the fields of media, education, and technology for the public opening of the Library of Congress's Culpeper campus	7/8/08	\$45,000
Lori Jahnke, Philadelphia, PA Amanda Watson, New Haven, CT	To analyze reports submitted by recipients of CLIR's Mellon Fellowship program for Dissertation Research in Original Sources	5/10/11	\$15,000
Jon Kertzer Seattle, WA	To research and explore nonprofit fundraising opportunities for archives and others in the field of recorded sound	1/11/2010	\$118,000
Todd Krater Lakemoor, IL	To provide services related to ongoing maintenance of CLIR's online application systems	9/3/2009	\$5,150

Recipient	Purpose	Authorized	Amount
Lehigh University Bethlehem, PA	2009 Hidden Collections grant to support the project, "The Moravian Community in the New World: The First 100 Years"	11/13/2009	\$90,552
Library of Congress Washington, DC	2008 Hidden Collections grant to support the project, "Library of Congress Multi-Sheet Map Series Collection: Africa"	12/1/2008	\$240,240
Litchfield Historical Society Litchfield, CT	2008 Hidden Collections grant to support the project, "Revolutionary Era and Early Republic Holdings"	12/1/2008	\$101,209
Marquette University Milwaukee, WI	2009 Hidden Collections grant to support the project, "Catholic Social Action Access Project"	11/13/2009	\$149,964
Shawn Martin Philadelphia, PA	To convene a meeting on the topic of sustainable open access business models for libraries	11/26/2008	\$5,000
Media Mechanics, Inc. San Francisco, CA	To produce a series of five radio programs focusing on recordings recently selected for inclusion in the Library of Congress National Recording Registry	10/15/2010	\$8,000
Holly Mengel and Courtney Smerz Philadelphia, PA	To conduct the workshop, "Archives for Non-Archivists" at Bryn Mawr, October 28-29, 2010	8/18/2010	\$5,150
Holly Mengel and Courtney Smerz Philadelphia, PA	To conduct the workshop, "Archives for Non-Archivists," June 14-15, 2011	3/8/2011	\$3,650
Kelly Miller Charlottesville, VA	To organize and manage the project "Best Practices for Scholarly Engagement with Hidden Special Collections and Archives"	12/1/2008	\$94,050
Kelly Miller Los Angeles, CA	To organize and manage the project, "Observations on Engagement with Hidden Special Collections and Archives," for the 2009 Hidden Collections grantees	4/1/2010	\$30,550
Newberry Library Chicago, IL	2009 Hidden Collections grant to support the project, "French Pamphlet Collections at the Newberry Library"	11/13/2009	\$488,179
New York University New York, NY	2008 Hidden Collections grant to support the project, "Records of the Communist Party, USA and Library of Reference Center for Marxist Studies"	12/1/2008	\$492,901
North Carolina State University Libraries Raleigh, NC	2009 Hidden Collections grant to support the project, "Changing the Landscape: Exposing the Legacy of Modernist Architects and Landscape Architects"	11/13/2009	\$221,023
Northeast Historic Film Bucksport, ME	2009 Hidden Collections grant to support the project, "Intellectual Access to Moving Images of Work Life, 1916-1950"	11/13/2009	\$214,626
Northeast Historic Film Bucksport, ME	2010 Hidden Collections grant to support the project, "Moving Images 1938-1940: Amateur Filmmakers Record the New York World's Fair and its Period"	12/16/2010	\$186,900

Recipient	Purpose	Authorized	Amount
Northwestern University Library Evanston, IL	2008 Hidden Collections grant to support the project, "Africana Posters: a collaboration with Northwestern University and Michigan State University"	12/1/2008	\$89,733
Jerry Persons San Mateo, CA	To conduct an in-depth survey of current publications, programs, and tools that generate or make use of Semantic Web, Linked Data, and RDF Triples Technologies	3/24/2011	\$40,000
Regents of the University of California Berkeley, CA	2010 Hidden Collections grant to support the project, "Cataloging Hidden Archives of the University of California Museum of Paleontology"	12/16/2010	\$236,200
Regents of the University of California Berkeley, CA	2009 Hidden Collections grant to support the project, "San Francisco Examiner Photograph Archive Project"	11/13/2009	\$306,446
Regents of the University of California Berkeley, CA	2008 Hidden Collections grant to support the project, "University and Jepson Herbaria"	12/1/2008	\$253,794
Karina Rodriguez Brighton, UK	To continue to serve as information director for the Association for Computing Machinery Journal on Computing and Cultural Heritage	12/23/2009	\$10,000
San Diego Historical Society San Diego, CA	2010 Hidden Collections grant to support the project, "Enhancing Access to the History of San Diego and the Border Region"	12/16/2010	\$162,100
Smithsonian Institution Washington, DC	2009 Hidden Collections grant to support the project, "Exposing Biodiversity Fieldbooks and Original Expedition Journals at the Smithsonian Institution"	11/13/2009	\$498,239
Smithsonian Institution/Freer Gallery of Art and Sackler Gallery Washington, DC	2011 Hidden Collections grant to support the project, "Islamic Arts of the Book at the Smithsonian: Providing for Research Across Disciplines"	12/16/2010	\$82,500
Stanford University Palo Alto, CA	2010 Hidden Collections grant to support the project, "Documenting Mexican American and Latino Civil Rights"	12/16/2010	\$349,300
Maureen Sullivan Annapolis, MD	To develop a workshop in support of the project ,Leadership Through New Communities of Knowledge	3/25/2010	\$5,800
Maureen Sullivan Annapolis, MD	To develop a workshop in support of the project, Leadership Through New Communities of Knowledge	2/4/2011	\$6,000
Syracuse University Syracuse, NY	2010 Hidden Collections grant to support the project, "Grove Press and a New American Morality"	12/16/2010	\$143,100
Tufts University Medford, MA	To perform the services set forth in proposal narrative to IMLS "Collaborative Planning for an Infrastructure to support Humanities Scholarship"	11/3/2009	\$25,000
University of Chicago Chicago, IL	2010 Hidden Collections grant to support the project, "The 'Color Curtain' Processing Project: Unveiling the University of Chicago's Black Metropolis"	12/16/2010	\$499,408

Recipient	Purpose	Authorized	Amount
University of California, Los Angeles Los Angeles, CA	To support the UCLA Library's undergraduate capstone seminars program	11/7/2008	\$10,000
University of Illinois Urbana-Champaign, IL	To provide basic maintenance for 169 collections held within the DLF American History online collections in the IMLS DCC repository	4/15/2011	\$12,000
University of Michigan Ann Arbor, MI	2008 Hidden Collections grant to support the project, "Collaboration in Cataloging: Islamic Manuscripts at Michigan"	12/1/2008	\$225,931
University of Nebraska- Lincoln Libraries Lincoln, NE	2010 Hidden Collections grant to support the project, "Major Railroad Archival Collections"	12/16/2010	\$208,500
University of North Carolina Chapel Hill, NC	2010 Hidden Collections grant to support the project, "The Pruitt and Shanks Photographic Collection"	12/16/2010	\$78,400
University of Pennsylvania Philadelphia, PA	2010 Hidden Collections grant to support the project, "Promoting Research Through Rare Book Cataloging Partnerships"	12/16/2010	\$490,700
University of Pennsylvania Philadelphia, PA	2008 Hidden Collections grant to support the project, "Hidden Collections in the Philadelphia Area: A Consortial Processing and Cataloging Initiative"	12/16/2008	\$500,000
University of Rochester Rochester, NY	To support four faculty research/undergraduate research behavior workshops in 2011, led by Nancy Fried Foster	12/12/2010	\$13,200
University of Rochester Rochester, NY	To support four workshops on faculty research behavior, led by Nancy Fried Foster	11/30/2009	\$12,000
University of Southern California Libraries Los Angeles, CA	2009 Hidden Collections grant to support the project, "Excavating L.A.: USC's Hidden Southern California Historical Collections"	11/13/2009	\$160,000
University of Texas Austin, TX	2010 Hidden Collections grant to support the project, "Revealing Texas Collections of Comedias Seltas"	12/16/2010	\$137,100
Elizabeth Waraska Los Angeles, CA	For assistance on strategic plan document for "Co-plan for Humanities Scholarship"	3/15/2011	\$21,000
WGBH Educational Foundation Boston, MA	2010 Hidden Collections grant to support the project, "Exposing Unknown Boston Local TV News Collections"	12/16/2010	\$311,000
Yale Peabody Museum of Natural History New Haven, CT	2010 Hidden Collections grant to support the project, "From DNA to Dinosaurs"	12/16/2010	\$409,300
Yale University New Haven, CT	2009 Hidden Collections grant to support the project, "Song, Speech, and Dance: Special Collections from the Recorded Sound Archives at Yale and Stanford Universities"	11/13/2009	\$457,776

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY AND INFORMATION RESOURCES

**FINANCIAL STATEMENTS
WITH
ADDITIONAL INFORMATION**

**FOR THE YEAR ENDED JUNE 30, 2011
WITH
INDEPENDENT AUDITORS' REPORT**

**STONE AND SPRING
Certified Public Accountants
Herndon, Virginia**

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY AND INFORMATION RESOURCES

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CERTIFIED PUBLIC ACCOUNTANTS
A Partnership of Professional Corporations

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Michael G. Spring, Jr., C.P.A.
Stephen C. Stone, C.P.A.

INDEPENDENT AUDITOR'S REPORT

To the Board of Directors
Council on Library and Information Resources
Washington, DC

We have audited the accompanying statement of financial position of the Council on Library and Information Resources (a nonprofit organization) as of June 30, 2011, and the related statement of activities and changes in net assets, and cash flows for the year then ended. These financial statements are the responsibility of the Council on Library and Information Resources' management. Our responsibility is to express an opinion on these financial statements based on our audit.

We conducted our audit in accordance with auditing standards generally accepted in the United States of America. Those standards require that we plan and perform the audit to obtain reasonable assurance about whether the financial statements are free of material misstatement. An audit includes examining, on a test basis, evidence supporting the amounts and disclosures in the financial statements. An audit also includes assessing the accounting principles used and significant estimates made by management, as well as evaluating the overall financial statement presentation. We believe that our audit provides a reasonable basis for our opinion.

In our opinion, the financial statements referred to above present fairly, in all material respects, the financial position of the Council on Library and Information Resources as of June 30, 2011, and the changes in its net assets and its cash flows for the year then ended in conformity with accounting principles generally accepted in the United States of America.

Our audit was conducted for the purpose of forming an opinion on the basic financial statements taken as a whole. The schedule of functional expenses on page 35 is presented for purposes of additional analysis and is not a required part of the basic financial statements. Such information is the responsibility of management and was derived from and relates directly to the underlying accounting and other records used to prepare the financial statements. The information has been subjected to the auditing procedures applied in the audit of the basic financial statements and certain additional procedures, including comparing and reconciling such information directly to the underlying accounting and other records used to prepare the financial statements or to the financial statements themselves, and other additional procedures in accordance with auditing standards generally accepted in the United States of America. In our opinion, the information is fairly stated in all material respects in relation to the basic financial statements taken as a whole.

Certified Public Accountants

Herndon, Virginia
September 19, 2011

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY AND INFORMATION RESOURCES

STATEMENT OF FINANCIAL POSITION

June 30, 2011

	<u>Unrestricted</u>	<u>Temporary Restricted</u>	<u>Total</u>
Assets:			
Cash and cash equivalents	\$ 167,141	\$ 2,913,315	\$ 3,080,456
Investments	101,037		101,037
Accounts receivable	-	66,988	66,988
Furniture and equipment, net	27,664	-	27,664
Other assets	99,947	-	99,947
Total Assets	<u>\$ 395,789</u>	<u>\$ 2,980,303</u>	<u>\$ 3,376,092</u>
Liabilities and Net Assets			
Accounts payable	\$ 33,116	\$ -	\$ 33,116
Capital lease	6,966	-	6,966
Accrued expenses	119,519	-	119,519
Total Liabilities	<u>\$ 159,601</u>	<u>\$ -</u>	<u>\$ 159,601</u>
Net Assets	<u>\$ 236,188</u>	<u>\$ 2,980,303</u>	<u>\$ 3,216,491</u>
Total Liabilities and Net Assets	<u><u>\$ 395,789</u></u>	<u><u>\$ 2,980,303</u></u>	<u><u>\$ 3,376,092</u></u>

The accompanying notes to financial statements
are an integral part of this statement.

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY AND INFORMATION RESOURCES

STATEMENT OF ACTIVITIES AND CHANGES IN NET ASSETS

For the Year Ended June 30, 2011

	Unrestricted	Temporary Restricted	Total
Revenue			
Grants and contracts	\$ 876,021	\$ 1,491,379	\$ 2,367,400
Contributions	692,855	14,500	707,355
Publication sales	15,476	-	15,476
Investment income/(loss)	37,803	10,726	48,529
Other income	178,153	9,050	187,203
	<u>\$ 1,800,308</u>	<u>\$ 1,525,655</u>	<u>\$ 3,325,963</u>
Net Assets released from restrictions			
Satisfaction of program restrictions	<u>\$ 1,425,789</u>	<u>\$ (1,425,789)</u>	<u>\$ -</u>
Total Revenue	<u>\$ 3,226,097</u>	<u>\$ 99,866</u>	<u>\$ 3,325,963</u>
Expenses			
Program services:			
Preservation	\$ 144,867	\$ -	\$ 144,867
Digital library	479,172	-	479,172
Leadership	190,569	-	190,569
Other	95,319	-	95,319
Cyberinfrastructure	34,179	-	34,179
International developments	113,272	-	113,272
The next scholar	1,617,698	-	1,617,698
Total Program Services	<u>\$ 2,675,076</u>	<u>\$ -</u>	<u>\$ 2,675,076</u>
Administration	<u>635,008</u>	<u>-</u>	<u>635,008</u>
Total Expenses	<u>\$ 3,310,084</u>	<u>\$ -</u>	<u>\$ 3,310,084</u>
Change in Net Assets	<u>\$ (83,987)</u>	<u>\$ 99,866</u>	<u>\$ 15,879</u>
Net Assets, Beginning of Year			
As previously reported	\$ 1,060,218	\$ 2,140,394	\$ 3,200,612
Adjustment for overstatement of unrestricted net assets	<u>(740,043)</u>	<u>740,043</u>	<u>-</u>
Balance at beginning of year as as restated	<u>\$ 320,175</u>	<u>\$ 2,880,437</u>	<u>\$ 3,200,612</u>
Net Assets, End of Year	<u>\$ 236,188</u>	<u>\$ 2,980,303</u>	<u>\$ 3,216,491</u>

The accompanying notes to financial statements
are an integral part of this statement.

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY AND INFORMATION RESOURCES

STATEMENT OF CASH FLOWS

For the year ended June 30, 2011

Operating Activities	
Change in net assets	\$ 15,879
Adjustments to reconcile change in net assets to net cash provided by (used) operating activities:	
Depreciation	14,560
Unrealized (gain) loss on investments	(1,037)
Realized (gain) loss on investments	(29,832)
(Increase) decrease in other assets	23,690
(Increase) decrease in accounts receivable	629,340
Increase (decrease) in accounts payable and accrued expenses	<u>15,430</u>
Net Cash Provided (used) by Operating Activities	<u>\$ 668,030</u>
Investing Activities	
Proceeds from sales of investments	820,022
Purchases of investments	(111,491)
Purchases of furniture and equipment	<u>(3,934)</u>
Net Cash Provided (Used) by Investing Activities	<u>\$ 704,597</u>
Financing Activities	
Principal payments on capital lease	<u>\$ (1,944)</u>
Net Cash Provided (Used) by Financing Activities	<u>\$ (1,944)</u>
Net Change in Cash and Cash equivalents	<u>\$ 1,370,683</u>
Cash and Cash Equivalents, Beginning of Year	<u>\$ 1,709,773</u>
Cash and Cash Equivalents, End of Year	<u><u>\$ 3,080,456</u></u>
Supplemental Cash Flow Information:	
Interest paid during the year	<u><u>\$ -</u></u>

The accompanying notes to financial statements are an integral part of this statement.

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY AND INFORMATION RESOURCES

NOTES TO FINANCIAL STATEMENTS

June 30, 2011

NOTE 1- Organization

The Council on Library and Information Resources is a not-for-profit organization incorporated under the laws of the District of Columbia in 1988 for the purpose of fostering, developing, and supporting systematic and purposeful collaboration in order to ensure the preservation of the published and documentary record in all formats and provide equitable access to that information.

The Council on Library and Information Resources operations are financed through contributions from colleges, universities and other organizations and through general support grants and restricted grants from private foundations and other sources. The Council on Library and Information Resources conducts its work directly through committees and working groups as well as through contracts with other organizations and individuals.

NOTE 2- Summary of Significant Accounting Policies

Basis of accounting - The accompanying financial statements of the Council on Library and Information Resources have been prepared on the accrual basis.

Grant revenue and recognition of grantor restrictions - The Council on Library and Information Resources reports grants as temporarily restricted support if they are received with grantor stipulations that limit the use of the grants as to time or purpose. When either condition is satisfied, temporarily restricted net assets are reclassified to unrestricted net assets and reported in the statement of activities and changes in net assets as net assets released from restrictions. Support that is restricted by the grantor is reported as an increase in unrestricted net assets if the restriction expires in the reporting period in which the support is recognized.

Contracts / Grants payable - Contracts made by the Council on Library and Information Resources are recorded as contracts payable and expensed at the time contracts are awarded. Current period expenses are adjusted for contract refunds or over appropriations when received.

Board designated net assets - From time to time, the Board of Directors designates a portion of unrestricted net assets for various short-term projects.

Cash and cash equivalents - For purposes of the statement of cash flows, cash and cash equivalents consist primarily of deposits in a money market account and investments with original maturities of 90 days or less.

Advertising costs - Advertising costs are expensed as incurred.

Accounts Receivable - Accounts receivable represent sponsor fees billings, and current unreimbursed expenses on various contracts. Allowance for doubtful accounts is normally recorded for amounts deemed as uncollectible. The Council on Library and Information Resources has not recorded any amount for the allowance for doubtful accounts because the Council on Library and Information Resources receives funds on a cost reimbursement basis and sponsorship revenues are current.

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY AND INFORMATION RESOURCES

NOTES TO FINANCIAL STATEMENTS

June 30, 2011

(Continued)

NOTE 2- Summary of Significant Accounting Policies (continued)

Functional allocation of expenses - Costs of the various programs have been summarized on a functional basis in the accompanying financial statements. Salaries and travel costs have been allocated directly to programs and administration on a time-allocated basis.

Furniture and Equipment - Furniture and equipment are recorded at cost, less accumulated depreciation. Depreciation expense is computed using the straight-line method over the estimated useful lives of the respective assets. Expenditures for maintenance and repairs are charged against income as incurred; betterments which increase the value or materially extend the life of the related assets are capitalized.

Contributions - The Council on Library and Information Resources records grant income as unrestricted, temporarily restricted, or permanently restricted support, depending upon the terms and conditions of the grant.

Fair value of financial instruments - Management estimates that the fair value of all financial instruments at June 30, 2011 does not differ materially from the aggregate carrying values reported in the accompanying statement of financial position due to the short term maturities of those instruments.

Use of estimates - The preparation of financial statements in conformity with generally accepted accounting principles requires management to make estimates and assumptions that affect the reported amounts of assets and liabilities and disclosure of contingent assets and liabilities at the date of the financial statements. Estimates also affect the reported amounts of revenues and expenses during the reporting period. Actual results could differ from those estimates.

NOTE 3- Furniture and Equipment

Furniture and equipment consist of the following:

Furniture and equipment	\$ 103,998
Less: Accumulated depreciation and amortization	<u>(76,334)</u>
	<u>\$ 27,664</u>

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY AND INFORMATION RESOURCES

NOTES TO FINANCIAL STATEMENTS

June 30, 2011

(Continued)

NOTE 4- Investments

The Council on Library and Information Resources has adopted SFAS No. 124, "Accounting for Certain Investments Held by Not-for-Profit Organizations." Under SFAS No. 124, investments in marketable securities with readily determinable fair values and all investments in debt securities are reported at their fair values in the statement of financial position. Unrealized gains and losses are included in the change in net assets. Investment income and gains restricted by a donor are reported as increases in unrestricted net assets if the restrictions are met (either by passage of time or by use) in the reporting period in which the income and gains are recognized.

Investment return consists of the following at June 30, 2011

	Gain/(loss) on <u>Investments</u>	Unrealized Gain/(loss) on <u>Investments</u>	<u>Fair Value</u>
Stocks	\$ 18,257	\$ 1,037	-
Bonds	-	-	-
Corporate fixed income	7,514	-	-
Government securities	-	-	-
Certificates of deposit	-	-	-
Mutual funds	<u>4,061</u>	<u>-</u>	<u>101,037</u>
Subtotal	<u>\$ 29,832</u>	<u>\$ 1,037</u>	<u>\$ 101,037</u>
Cash and cash equivalents	<u>-</u>	<u>-</u>	<u>\$ 3,080,456</u>
Total	<u>\$ 29,832</u>	<u>\$ 1,037</u>	

The following schedule summarizes the investment and cash equivalent return and its classification in the statement of activities for the year ended June 30, 2011:

	<u>Unrestricted</u>	Temporarily <u>Restricted</u>	<u>Total</u>
Interest and dividends	\$ 6,934	\$ 10,726	\$ 17,660
Realized gains (losses)	29,832	-	29,832
Unrealized gains (losses)	<u>1,037</u>	<u>-</u>	<u>1,037</u>
Total investment return	<u>\$ 37,803</u>	<u>\$ 10,726</u>	<u>\$ 48,529</u>

NOTE 5 - Income Taxes

The Council on Library and Information Resources is exempt from federal income taxes under Section 501(c)(3) of the Internal Revenue Code and applicable regulations of the District of Columbia.

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY AND INFORMATION RESOURCES

NOTES TO FINANCIAL STATEMENTS

June 30, 2011
(Continued)

NOTE 6 - Net Assets released from Restrictions

Net assets were released from grantor restrictions by incurring expenses satisfying the restricted purposes or by occurrence of other events specified by grantors.

NOTE 7 - Retirement Plan

Employees are eligible for participation in the Council on Library and Information Resources defined contribution retirement annuity program ("the Plan") administered through the TIAA/CREF insurance companies. Individual contracts issued under the Plan provide for full and immediate vesting of the Council on Library and Information Resources contributions. The Council on Library and Information Resources contributes 15% of employees' salaries to the Plan each year. The Council on Library and Information Resources contributions were \$132,214 in 2011.

NOTE 8 - Concentrations of Credit Risk

Financial instruments which potentially subject the Council on Library and Information Resources to concentrations of credit risk consist primarily of cash equivalents. At June 30, 2011, the Council on Library and Information Resources held \$2,709,674 in investments. This amount is not insured by the Federal Deposit Insurance Corporation. In addition, cash in the bank included in noninterest bearing accounts at June 30, 2011 is fully insured under FDIC. Uninsured amounts that are interest bearing are insured up to \$250,000. At June 30, 2011, the uninsured cash balance was \$154,555. In 2010, the FDIC started a program called the Dodd-Frank provision that provides unlimited coverage on deposits for noninterest bearing account holders. The program ends December 31, 2012.

The Council on Library and Information Resources received \$1,902,567 from one organization which represents 57 % of total revenue.

NOTE 9 - Accounts Receivable

	June 30, <u>2011</u>
Account balances are aged as follows	
Current	\$ 50,939
30 - 60 days	16,049
60 - 90 days	-
Over 90 days	-
Less: Allowance for doubtful accounts	<u>-</u>
Total Accounts Receivable	<u>\$ 66,988</u>

NOTE 10 - Commitments

The Council on Library and Information Resources has entered into a noncancelable operating lease agreement for its office space which expires in August, 2018. Rental expense, for the year ending June 30, 2011 was \$258,873. The Council on Library and Information Resources is also leasing a copier under a capital lease. This lease will expire in January 2015.

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY AND INFORMATION RESOURCES

NOTES TO FINANCIAL STATEMENTS

June 30, 2011
(Continued)

NOTE 10 - Commitments (continued)

Future minimum lease payments under all leases with initial remaining noncancelable lease terms in excess of one year are as follows:

Period Ending <u>June 30,</u>	<u>Capital Lease</u>	<u>Operating Leases</u>
2012	\$ 1,944	\$ 267,934
2013	1,944	277,312
2014	1,944	287,018
2015	1,134	297,063
2016	-	318,221
2017 and beyond		385,518
Total minimum lease payments	\$ 6,966	\$ <u>1,833,066</u>
Less: Amount representing interest. Present value of net minimum lease payments	<u>-</u> <u>\$ 6,966</u>	

NOTE 11- Board Designated Net Assets Funds

The Board of Directors voted to designate net assets of \$400,000 for operating reserves.

NOTE 12 - Fair Value of Financial Instruments

The carrying amounts reflected in the balance sheets for cash, cash equivalents, loans and notes payable approximate the respective fair values due to the short maturities of those instruments. SFAS 157 requires a fair value hierarchy to be used to prioritize valuation inputs into three levels:

Level 1 – Quoted prices (unadjusted) in active markets for identical assets or liabilities.

Level 2 – Observable inputs other than the quoted prices included in Level 1.

Level 3 – Unobservable inputs.

Fair values of assets and liabilities measured on a nonrecurring basis at June 30, 2011 are as follows:

Description	Fair Value	(Level 1)	(Level 2)	(Level 3)	(Losses)
Long-lived assets held for sale	\$ 101,037	-	\$ 101,037	\$ -	-

Long-lived assets have been valued using a market approach. The values were determined using market prices of similar long-lived assets.

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY AND INFORMATION RESOURCES

NOTES TO FINANCIAL STATEMENTS

June 30, 2011
(Concluded)

NOTE 13 – Reclassification of Prior Amounts

Net assets that should have been recorded as temporarily restricted net assets were recorded incorrectly as unrestricted net assets. This was corrected in the current year and is reflected as an adjustment to beginning unrestricted and temporarily restricted net assets. The net increase/(decrease) in the change to net assets was \$0

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY AND INFORMATION RESOURCES
SCHEDULE OF FUNCTIONAL EXPENSES
For The Year Ended June 30, 2011

	<u>The Next</u>	<u>Cyber</u>	<u>Leadership</u>	<u>Preservation</u>	<u>Digital</u>	<u>Other</u>	<u>International</u>	<u>Total</u>	<u>Administration</u>	<u>Total</u>
	<u>Scholar</u>	<u>Infrastructure</u>	<u>Leadership</u>	<u>Preservation</u>	<u>Library</u>	<u>Other</u>	<u>Developments</u>	<u>Program</u>	<u>Administration</u>	<u>Total</u>
Employee costs	\$ 798,403	\$ 5,683	\$ 97,505	\$ 31,537	\$ 242,961	\$ 421	\$ -	\$ 1,176,510	\$ 105,432	\$ 1,281,942
Professional Services and contracts	60,185	7,258	-	87,640	49,515	396	2,813	207,807	100,720	308,527
Fellowships, scholarships and interns	370,724	-	10,000	-	5,000	-	-	385,724	3,198	388,922
Grants	23,094	-	-	-	-	-	-	23,094	-	23,094
Communications	60,885	275	225	-	5,792	1,123	-	68,300	26,978	95,278
Travel and meetings	268,539	21,012	66,167	758	155,234	79,863	110,459	702,032	63,101	765,133
Publications	1,173	-	72	10,649	232	6,818	-	18,944	9,396	28,340
Office operations	34,695	(49)	16,600	14,283	20,438	6,698	-	92,665	326,183	418,848
Total	\$ 1,617,698	\$ 34,179	\$ 190,569	\$ 144,867	\$ 479,172	\$ 95,319	\$ 113,272	\$ 2,675,076	\$ 635,008	\$ 3,310,084

The accompanying notes to financial statements are an integral part of this statement.

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY AND INFORMATION RESOURCES

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